

METHODS OF USING THE MYTEST PROGRAM IN THE ORGANIZATION OF FINAL CONTROL PROCESSES FOR STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Аннотация. В данной статье описаны методы использования программы MyTest при организации процессов итогового контроля студентов высших учебных заведений и важные аспекты данной программы при организации процессов итогового контроля студентов высших учебных заведений.

Annotation. This article describes the methods of using the MyTest program in the organization of final control processes for students of higher education institutions and the important aspects of this program in the organization of final control processes for students of higher education institutions.

Ключевые слова. Программа MyTest, создание тестов, выполнение тестов, ответы и результаты, онлайн-тесты.

Keywords. MyTest program, test creation, test execution, answers and results, online tests.

Final control processes for students of higher education institutions are carried out to evaluate students' study and learning processes. These processes include monitoring based on students' knowledge and skills, understanding, mastery, analytical thinking, performance and other important skills. These processes can be carried out in several stages during the academic year. Final control processes can be determined through evaluation forms carried out during the academic year. These forms are a combination of course work, practical exercises, tests and trials, projects, coursework, graduation work and other assessment methods. These assessments help to determine the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process and the level of student achievement. Final control procedures are mastered at the end of the school year and can be used by teachers, programmers, mentors, etc. to participate in the evaluation of students. The main goal is to determine how well students develop in self-assessment and learning processes, and to help students achieve higher levels of knowledge and skills. Final assessment processes help to assess the level of students' mastery, the progress they have made in the learning processes and the effectiveness of the learning processes by reading. The MyTest program can be used to organize the final control processes of students in higher education institutions. MyTest is an automated learning process that allows students to create, edit and grade electronic tests. This program helps to solve many problems of students' acquisition, organization of tests and calculation of grades. The MyTest program automates the process of mastering tests, organizing tests and calculating grades

and provides convenience to students. This software helps in updating students' test procedures, quick calculation of results and evaluation of learning process with grades.

Methods of using the MyTest program in the organization of final control processes for students of higher education institutions create convenience for students and teachers. MyTest is a widely used platform for organizing online tests, evaluating answers and calculating results. The following methods represent the basic processes of using MyTest:

-teachers can create tests on the MyTest platform. These tests can consist of questions on any topic, multiple choice, or true or false questions. In the process of creating a test, the topic of the test, the total number, the choice options for each question and the correct answers should be entered.

- structured tests are distributed according to students' time and study programs. Teachers can distribute the tests to the students at a fixed time interval. It helps in determining the level of students' attainment, assesses the stage of learning and assesses the students' achievement of higher levels of knowledge and skills.

-students will receive a password upon login to complete tests on the MyTest platform. Students must mark the correct answers to the tests online. Teachers can open tests at specified time intervals and see the final results.

-MyTest software automatically scores the questions and results answered correctly by students. Teachers will have statistics on the MyTest platform to study the results. This data helps teachers to analyze the level of achievement of students, skills and effectiveness of learning processes.

-MyTest software provides students with results electronically. Students help teachers review test results, receive grades, and assess their personal development. And teachers use results-based analysis and evaluations in the teaching process.

The MyTest program provides convenience and automated assessment in the organization of final control processes in higher education institutions. It is a convenient and effective tool for teachers to assess the students' level of achievement and the knowledge and skills they have learned. Also, the MyTest program allows you to archive the results of students and refer to these results electronically.

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